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An Eye Blink Reflex Model based on an Intracellular Timing Mechanism in Purkinje Cells and on a Conditioned Stimulus Segregation Mechanism in the Nucleus Interpositus might explain the Double Peaks Phenomenon.

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An Eye Blink Reflex Model based on an Intracellular Timing Mechanism in Purkinje Cells and on a Conditioned Stimulus Segregation Mechanism in the Nucleus Interpositus might explain the Double Peaks Phenomenon.

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Abbreviations :

AF	ascending fiber	IO(N)	inferior olive (neuron)
CF	climbing fiber	ISI	interstimulus interval
CN	cerebellar nuclei	LTP/D	long term potentiation/depression
CR	conditioned reflex	MF	mossy fiber
CS	conditioned stimulus	MLI	molecular layer interneuron
EBR	eye blink reflex	NI	nucleus interpositus
eNC	excitatory nucleo-cortical	NON	nucleo-olivary neuron
GoC	Golgi cell	NuC	nuclear cell
GrC	granule cell	OCNO	olivo-cerebello-nucleo-olivary
GrL	granular layer	PN	pontine nuclei
HP	hyperpolarization	PPC	'privileged partner connection'
HP-R	hyperpolarization-rebound	PuC	Purkinje cell
iNC	inhibitory nucleo-cortical	SS	synapse strength
		US	unconditioned stimulus

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

ABSTRACT

[1] [Johansson et al. \(2014\)](#) inferred from his research that an mGluR7 based mechanism might exist that endows the PuC itself with an intracellular chemical timing mechanism (ICTM), and suggests that CRs are based on it.

Following up on his thinking line, it will be argued here

- 1) that ICTMs in PuCs better be informed of the presence of a CS by way of CFs and not of PFs.
- 2) that, when the NI identifies a CS by associating it with the US, CS carrying MFs onto NONs are LTP'd until they are able to HP-R IONs which then in turn can alert the PuCs by CF route of the presence of a CS.
- 3) and that different CSs – when they occur - segregate their share of neurocircuitry resources in the NI, as to avoid CS interference effects.

Accordingly it is hypothesized that an active segregation process is initiated in the NI from the moment that two CSs start to 'compete' for the EBR.

A demo program has been written to 'simulate' and 'visualize' such a segregation process 'in action'. It was possible to tune parameters as to evoke also the 'double peaks phenomenon' which is transiently observed in the beginning of a training process (as well as in the juvenile multi-innervation phase of CFs onto PuCs) when animals are trained with two different CSs with different ISIs. It provides insights as to the details of the process which might be in play in the NI in vivo.

INTRODUCTION

Johansson demonstrated the presence of an ICTM, but the biochemical details of it are still unknown. His speculations about form and function may be described as follows :

- a) the CS triggers in the PuC a 'timer initiating process' by a chemical cascade of conformational changes in 'recording proteins'.

[2] Johansson et al. (2014)

“At the onset of the conditional stimulus the ‘recorder’ proteins start changing in a predictable way. We assume four possible conformational states: ‘-’, A, B and C. Suppose that for the first 100 ms they are all in the ‘-’ state, between, say, 100-250 ms most are in the A state, between 200-350 ms most are in the B state and between 300-400 ms in the C state.”

- b) strong CF firing activates this conformation to 'prime' / release / put in operational position or made a class of timer units (preexisting in 'sleeping state' or produced ?), the choice of which depends on the actual state of the conformation at US time : a timer selecting process.

[2] Johansson et al. (2014)

“Assume further that the recorder proteins interact with the unconditional stimulus in different ways depending on when it arrives. Suppose that when they are still in the ‘-’ state there is no effect, but when they are in either the A, B or C states, different activation sites are available for the unconditional stimulus. Activating the recorder proteins in one of the states may then cause translation or activation of particular timer units. In this way the learning mechanism selects appropriate timer units (the effector components that generate a response at the right time).”

- c) when triggered by the CS, the selected timer units are able to hyperpolarize [HP] the PuC after a time that grossly matches the duration (or a bit less since CR onset is to occur before the US) of the recording protein activation that led to their selection : a timer triggering process.

[2] Johansson et al. (2014)

“Our finding that the adaptive time course of the Purkinje cell conditioned response depends on a mechanism in the cell itself suggests that a glutamate trigger from parallel fibers activates a cellular mechanism with a particular delay after which a hyperpolarizing response with a specific duration is turned on.”

An EBR is triggered by the ICTM HP'ing PuCs, which causes a pause in their firing, disinhibiting the NI moments before the expected US.

Classically, this firing pause is explained by LTD of PF-PuC synapses induced by CFs firing at US time and affecting only those synapses which happened to be presynaptically activated at that precise time, a strategy that assumes a network based timing mechanism (NBTM) .

Johansson however demonstrated that the ICTM works independently of any timing signal that might come in over the PFs, by using the technique of ‘drowning’ all PF traffic in a massive current injection, thereby obliterating any NBTM effect : a perplexing finding.

[3] Johansson et al. (2016)

“A recent study provides evidence for a radically new view of the mechanisms for motor timing in the cerebellum.

Contrary to the predictions of existing models, pairing a CS consisting of direct stimulation of the parallel fibers with a US consisting of direct climbing fiber stimulation led to a Purkinje cell CR that was adaptively timed.

That is, the cell reached maximum suppression <75 ms before the onset of the US regardless of CS-US interval.

This was an unexpected finding because with direct stimulation of parallel fibers, any temporal patterns of granule cell activity are presumably bypassed.”

An EBR simulation study of Medina and Mauk [4] Medina and Mauk (2000) - relying on an NBTM - demonstrated that quite some complications can arise, which an ICTM apparently avoids by not engaging synapse plasticity (and hence the use of LTD) : Johansson demonstrated it and others observed it too.

[5] Johansson et al. (2018)

“Although we agree with most investigators that LTD probably has an important role in other forms of motor learning, the present results clearly support the conclusion, that a classical conditioning protocol does not cause any significant LTD and that, therefore, the learning of the Purkinje cell CR in classical conditioning is not due to LTD but involves a different kind of learning mechanism.”

[6] Ten Brinke et al. (2015)

“LTD seems neither necessary nor sufficient for eyeblink conditioning, as selective genetic or pharmacological blockage of parallel fiber to Purkinje cell LTD expression does not significantly impair eyeblink conditioning (Welsh et al., 2005; Schonewille et al., 2011).”

In fact an ICTM might very well ‘cohabitate’ with an NBTM if the former does not tamper with the synapse tuning realized by the latter. An NBTM seems more suited for the ‘sculpting’ of signals over whole time intervals while an ICTM is more appropriate for the generation of a brisk signal at a specific moment only. PuCs might combine the two functionalities and Johansson realizes it.

[7] Johansson et al. (2015)

In other learning situations, where peripheral mechanisms can provide a richer temporal variation in the input to the granule cell layer, temporal coding in the parallel fiber input to Purkinje cells would be available. Under these conditions, synaptic weight changes such as LTD at parallel fiber synapses could play their part in establishing a temporal profile to learned responses. It will be important to determine whether such synaptic changes operate in parallel with the mGluR7-mediated postsynaptic temporal learning mechanism identified here.

However, Johansson's experimental setup clearly implies that the ICTM is triggered by a signal coming in over the PFs (which could be interfering / disrupting for signals meant for the NBTM).

Although his assumption is in line with a widespread conviction that PFs are the carriers of the CS which is to trigger the PuCs to start their timing function, it is to be considered that this aspect of the demonstration might be an artefact, and that, instead, CFs are the CS 'announcers'.

It is possible to conceive a working EBR model (and by generalization a CR model) based on an ICTM controlled by CFs, an 'in silico simulation' being used in support of it.

METHOD

Large parts of this article are argumentation and analysis of observations from past research on the NI.

In support of the argumentation, a demo program was written in Visual FoxPro 9.0 to display graphically and dynamically the hypothesized CS segregation process in the NI. Observations made 'in cerebello' were 'translated' into code and parameters were tuned until the desired result was achieved, thereby proving the 'feasibility' of it 'in silico' and providing insights in the process as well.

In this article screenshots ('still images') and videolinks (clickable in the PDF file) are used to render the demo.

1) THE CS ENTRY ROUTE

A) PFs

While Johansson rules out the PFs as the carriers of a time diversified signal useful for the EBR, his experimental approach at the same time points to the PFs as the carriers of the CS .

Yet, there are some considerations to make about CS carrying PFs :

a) PFs POSE A CS POWER ISSUE :

CS carrying PFs are but a small fraction of the total PF traffic (considering also that all possible CS variants should have the possibility to be represented in it), and hence the number of engaged ICTMs (to be initiated and triggered at synapse level) will be small too : more or less equalling the number of CS carrying PFs that contact the PuC.

Ultimately, a PuC has to be HP'd as a whole, and most probably a significant population of timer units must cooperate to achieve it (evidently, injecting 'massive current' in the PFs will trigger lots of timer units).

Since it is improbable that the number of PFs used by a CS can be 'boosted', there might be far too few engaged ICTMs to elicit PuC HP by combined effort.

Having timers for a specific CS distributed over several PuCs is of no avail either : each PuC still must have enough cooperating timers 'on board' to achieve HP .

Hence, it raises severe doubts that the implementation of CRs by a microzone can be done in a 'distributed' way : each PuC parcelling its load of timer units to contribute 'a little bit' in each CR .

It is also improbable that just a few activated PF-PuC synapses can generate the required amount of timer units, especially since the timers need to stay located at these same PF-PuC synapses to be triggered by them, while HP requires a PuC wide process.

PFs, crossing orthogonally the dendritic PuC trees, are topologically always bound to parcellate the PF-PuC synapse and timer population in function of PF signal identity.

b) PFs POSE A CS IDENTIFICATION ISSUE :

How are ICTMs to recognize a PF signal to be a CS amongst all the other PF traffic affecting the same PuC, and how is the PuC to be safeguarded from being triggered by 'false positives' ?

[6] Ten Brinke et al. (2015)

“Hidden within this sea of parallel fibers are signals encoding the green LED light, which by default is a neutral stimulus.

Only on the condition that it is consistently paired with the air puff and only by virtue of the Purkinje cell's capacity to forge associations between parallel and climbing fiber signals will one learn to perform a well-timed, conditional blink response (CR) upon exposure to the light, which is thusly called the conditional stimulus (CS).” (The classical view !)

Before training, PF signals evidently cannot yet be 'tagged' as to be a CS, meaning that ICTMs will be continuously initiated by all PF traffic, in expectation of a possible US to come after - an energy consuming process running idle most of the time.

During training, when a consistent US appears, timers tuned to a specific delay will appear, but they will be surrounded by quite a population of spuriously tuned timers, since any initiated ICTM will 'deliver' some timers as the US 'strikes' : if it is argued that these timers will be so sparse as not to be able to HP a PuC, then it is also admitted that a power issue exists, but with the huge amount of total PF traffic in mind it would be surprising if they were sparse.

Hence, after training, with all timers 'in standby', the spurious ones might also trigger HP of the PuC, and with no US following after such a 'false start', extinction steps in.

I didn't encounter comments on extinction regarding the ICTM, but I presume that HP of the PuC not followed by a US will do it.

With this extinction not being synapse specific, it will affect timers PuC wide - including CS dedicated ones - declining their number, and this already inbetween trials.

We may have been put 'on the wrong foot' by assuming that the CS comes in over the PFs.

Maybe a 'non-orthogonal input' is better, and then we have to consider AFs and CFs.

B) AFs

It is to be expected that a microzone dedicated to e.g. EBR musculature primarily receives MF input which is directly related to it : motor command corrolary discharge, US receptive field modalities

Other modalities are not forbidden, but it would be odd that the GrL of the microzone would have been prewired to receive MFs carrying all the potential CS modalities, since they are 'neutral' in origin (while it is just the attractiveness of the PF system to be 'broadband' in this respect) .

If nonetheless MFs deliver potential CS modalities to the microzone, to be relayed to AFs, a distribution issue arises : if evenly distributed all over the microzone, each PuC receiving AFs from all modalities, then we have again a parcellation (and a HP power issue) inside the PuC, the problem being transferred from PF-PuC synapses to AF-PuC synapses.

Only 'mapped' distribution can avoid this : each patch in a microzone receiving just one 'potential' CS modality (and just one variant of it), but - admittedly - the idea that there could be enough patches to accommodate all the CS possibilities looks highly unrealistic.

All these arguments together surely are not in favour of CS carrying AFs.

C) CFs

This leaves us with the CFs : CFs can announce the US to the PuCs, so why could CFs also not announce the CS ?

Considering 'distribution', they have a huge advantage : they don't 'parcellate' the PuC, the PuCs they contact are wholly 'their PuCs', engaging the totality of their ICTMs, posing no power issue.

On top of that CFs deliver such a strong signal that the PuC (its ICTMs) cannot mistake it for a signal coming in by alternative routes (PFs, AFs), assuming that ICTMs implement a threshold to distinguish the CF signals by their force from other signals (but flooding PFs by massive current injection can fool such a system) .

However, if CFs are to be the messengers of the CS, we should shift our attention to the NI and explain how an in origin neutral signal is to be recognized as a 'CS' and how this CS can be made to use the CF route.

D) RECAPITULATION

When PFs are considered to bring in the CS, it should be realized that each individual potential CS can only be sparsely represented in the PF mass.

As a result it poses a power problem (not enough timers cooperating to HP a PuC), and an identification problem (how is a PuC to recognize a CS in all the traffic) .

AFs are considered as an alternative CS input option, but unless they are 'mapped' onto the microzone they suffer from the same drawbacks as PFs, and the idea that ab initio 'neutral' CSs could already be prewired to be 'mapped' onto these specific microzones feels unacceptable.

CFs are much more promising candidates for signalling CS input : 'taking the PuC as a whole' they pose no power problem, but it shifts the focus onto the NI as the site where the identification problem has to be solved.

2) THE NI IDENTIFIES THE CS BY ASSOCIATION WITH THE US

The identification of a predicting CS necessarily must start with the detection of repeated coincident firing of MFs and CFs, and the CN (in casu the NI) is in a position to do that since it receives collaterals from both, many agree to that.

Boele et al. showed an increase in originally very sparse CS carrying PN-NI (MF collateral) fibers in EBR trained animals : a strong argument that the NI is the site where CS identification occurs.

[8] Boele et al. (2013)

“We demonstrate that pavlovian eyeblink conditioning in adult mice can induce robust axonal growth and synapse formation in the cerebellar nuclei.”

While the microzones for protective reflexes primarily get MF input from US modalities, the set of MF collaterals converging onto the NI should be much more encompassing and offer a sea of information of all kinds of modalities which comprise at least all those which are eligible to become a CS .

So the MF collateral tract onto the NI may be sparse in fibers, but it is broadband in content, and each fiber has the potentiality to LTP its connections and to multiply its terminals.

We have to consider :

A) THE ASSOCIATION PROBLEM

NuCs have been seen to develop LTP at the MF-NuC synapse when MF and CF firing coincides, but the underlying plasticity inducing system is peculiar : it does not rely on postsynaptic depolarization since a system in which the pre- and postsynaptic partners show intrinsic firing continually generates 'false coincidences'.

[9] Nishiyama (2014)

“It should be noted that excitatory inputs in the nucleus largely consist of mossy fibers (carrying CS) and inputs from the inferior olive (carrying US) . It is crucially important to determine which signal (CS vs. US) is strengthened in the nucleus through the structural plasticity described above. Experimental data and computer simulation indicate that CS pathway is strengthened in the nucleus (Medina Mauk, 1999; Ohyama et al., 2006; Steinmetz et al., 1989; Tracy, Thompson, Krupa, Thompson, 1998); thus, the structural plasticity in excitatory synapses is most likely to occur at mossy fiber inputs. This possibility was recently confirmed by Boele, Koekkoek, De Zeeuw, & Ruigrok (2013) .”

[10] (Pugh et al. 2009)

“Because of spontaneous firing, any mossy-fiber-dependent excitatory postsynaptic currents (EPSPs) has a reasonable chance of overlapping temporally with an action potential in a nuclear cell. Therefore, the Hebbian condition of correlated pre- and postsynaptic spiking arises randomly, which is predicted to yield a noisy signal.”

“In the deep cerebellar nuclei, Hebbian patterns of coincident synaptic excitation and postsynaptic firing fail to induce long-term increases in the strength of excitatory inputs.”

“Such results indicate that circuits with intrinsically active neurons have rules for information transfer and storage that distinguish them from other brain regions.”

So it appears that PuC triggered NuC HP-R is used as a more reliable condition to induce LTP on the active synapses.

The HP-R causing PuC - of course - has been triggered by the same CF firing that affected the NuCs and hence can provide the necessary second component for the coincidence detection.

To induce LTP in the 'target' cell, however, the two components must converge onto this cell, and a detour via the PuCs creates a serious mapping problem : the axons of the PuCs that were affected by the same CFs that connect to a particular set of NuCs must find their way back to this particular set.

In a separate article I argued that this is indeed the case (please note the concept of 'nanoloops' in the citation since the term is used later on).

[11] Beunis (2021a)

“In the CN a peculiar asymmetry in the synapsing of PuC axons onto NuCs has been observed : while PuC axons fan out to hundreds of NuCs, the axon terminals can exhibit particularly dense synapsing onto specific NuCs. It is suggested that such a 'privileged partner connection' (PPC) between PuCs and NuCs only exists when both receive excitation from the same CF, meaning that OCNO-loops are being 'closed' at an almost cellular resolution, hence far more refined than for a closure on the scope of a microzone.”

“While 'OCNO-loop philosophy' only requires that the cortical microzone which is 'alerted' by CFs should return its output to the population of NuCs that was synchronously alerted by the collaterals of these same CFs, PPCs would refine the resolution of the closure of these loops almost to the level of individual PuC-NuC partners. I would suggest to refer to the 'tiny OCNO loops' created through PPC formation as 'nanoloops'. Having a fine resolution of OCNO nanoloops inside a microzone allows for task diversification along a supplementary dimension, say when an MF map is projected onto the population of nanoloops. In the CN, receiving MF collaterals, it might allow for the segregated processing of different points (or small subregions) in this map by dedicated nanoloop groups.”

B) THE MAPPING PROBLEM OF THE MFs

Now consider a microzone and a subregion of the NI dedicated to the EBR and accept that 'nanoloops' exist, meaning that only a PuC (group) which is innervated by the same CF that innervates a NuC(group) is able to cause HP-R in this NuC (group) by virtue of the heavily LTP'd PuC-NuC connection between the two (the PPC).

When an EBR related US (e.g. puff of air on the cornea) triggers CFs to fire, it possesses no clues as to favour certain PuC/NuC groups above others in this microzone or NI subregion : it 'alerts' the whole EBR microzone and EBR NI subregion.

On the scope of the EBR region the CF (collateral) projection onto it can be considered to contain a 'homogeneous map' : the US signal is the same on all lines but the EBR region nonetheless has a fine resolution of nanoloops.

The collateral MF projection onto the EBR region, however, contains a set of different signals (at least all CSs 'in spe'), and this map might be orderly (topically structured) or 'scrambled'.

Let's consider the two extremes of the 'mapping situation' :

a) CONSEQUENCES OF VERY ORDERLY MF MAPPING ONTO THE NI :

It means that MF collaterals with same content stay anatomically close together when projecting onto the NI.

In this situation the MF collaterals can have a point to point connection with NuCs : MFs don't need to form spreading terminal axon arborizations, and NuCs don't need to have large dendritic trees to gather information from a larger area.

In this case, an MF-CS that consistently coincides with CF-US firing can be LTP'd in the very restricted NuC group that happens to be appositioned to the involved MFs that synapse upon them.

This group in turn has a restricted group of PuCs in the microzone as partners (although scattered if the CFs collateralize widely) and with PPCs between PuC axons and partner NuCs it involves a restricted group of nanoloops.

On condition that the PuCs in such nanoloops are made 'aware' of the LTP going on in the NuCs (see later) they can take care with their ICTM to generate a CR for this particular CS, while a different group (of other nanoloops) will do so for another CS coming in by different MFs.

In this way different CSs are handled in a segregated fashion, thanks to the precise mapping and thanks to the PPCs between the PuCs and the NuCs.

The PuC CR is channelled primarily to the partner NuCs in the NI (and more diffusely to the others), to disinhibit the EBR NI region, but since it implies a very restricted recruitment of nanoloops (and CS MFs are sparse to begin with as Boele observed) we may doubt if enough 'power' can be generated to produce an overt CR (PuC-HP in a restricted group unable to disinhibit activity in the global NI EBR region significantly) .

Hence again we encounter here a 'power problem' but now on the scale of the PuC population involved in evoking a CR in the NI (while the earlier mentioned power problem for timers inside a PuC concerned evoking the HP in the PuC itself) .

An MF map projected like this onto the NI EBR region would also leave a majority of nanoloops unused since we may assume that the majority of MF inputs are not eligible to be CSs - i.e. if we consider this region to be just involved with the EBR and with nothing else.

Such a map would have to be repeated for every reflex region (not just the EBR) and hence the next option seems more likely :

b) CONSEQUENCES OF 'SCRAMBLED MF MAPPING' ONTO THE NI :

In this other extreme MFs spread their terminals to distribute the CS over a large area, and NuCs spread their dendritic arbours to gather information from a large area.

In this second scenario we might end up with a situation in which all NuCs of the EBR region, and all PuCs in the connected microzone have a joint but even share in effectuating the CR, since a widely distributed CS engages all the nanoloops of the subregion.

However, as already mentioned, the ICTM does not lend itself to a 'distributed scenario' in which a restricted group of timers per PuC (but in all PuCs of the microzone) would contribute 'a little bit' to the CR.

Let's assume for a moment that - after enough MF-NuC LTP - ALL these PuCs develop enough ICTM 'power' to HP-R NuCs which - all together - are also able to elicit a CR .

The problem which is now going to arise, though, is one of CS interference when another CS is introduced, a CS which is also going 'to make use' of all the nanoloops, and so, with all NuCs being 'sensitive' to all CS MF inputs - not able to discriminate them - a 'light' CS and a 'tone' CS might trigger each other's ICTMs ('cross-modal transfer'), provoking double-peaked CRs if the respective ISIs are different.

In vivo, it is observed that there can be terminal sprouting of collateral MFs [8] Boele et al. (2013) and that dendritic arbours of NuCs can be very extending.

[12] Uusisaari et al. (2011)

"Because some of the CN neurons have very large and complex dendritic arborizations that may span large regions or nearly an entire CN subnucleus (Chan-Palay, 1977; Sultan et al. 2003), complex dendritic interactions between synaptic inputs originating from MF, CF and local interneurons can be assumed."

Is the situation in vivo some compromise between the two extremes ?

We may expect the MF collateral tract not to be completely scrambled so that fibers of like modality find themselves still in each other's vicinity, and the formation of PPCs is also bound to be restricted to the 'reach' of PuC terminal axon spread, which probably cannot cover a whole NI subregion.

The terminal MF sprouting however might be a dynamic way to recruit more nanoloops 'at the neighbours' to gather and join forces for the generation of a CR, and NuCs 'extending their antennae' might be necessary to locate the more dispersed CS carrying MF terminals.

But again : interference problems arise when suddenly 'a neighbour decides' that he has to develop a CR for 'his own' CS, and wants to enroll part of a population of nanoloops already in use by another CS. So, if CSs have no share of nanoloops 'allotted' to them for personal use, they will have to compete and 'fight' for them.

c) RECAPITULATION

Strict MF mapping onto the NI might be a structural way to 'segregate' CS handling with only the nanoloops appositioned to MF-CS inputs engaged in generating the respective CRs, but can such a small nanoloop group power up a CR ?

Considering that the MF map might as well be scrambled to begin with, the option of 'distributed' CS handling is examined, but in fact it forces individual PuCs to implement CS segregation, a scenario already criticized for its potential 'power problem' for timers to HP a PuC .

Moreover, individual NuCs being potentially sensitive to several CSs would involve a great risk of CS interference.

Taking all this into account, it is suggested that the nanoloops themselves (by way of their NuCs) have a dynamic way to segregate CSs when they arise in vivo, and that in the meanwhile MF sprouting is a means to engage enough nanoloops to evoke an overt CR.

3) THE NI SENDS THE CS TO THE PUCS BY WAY OF THE NUCLEO-OLIVARY ROUTE

The question of how a PuC is to recognize a signal to be a CS was already raised.

I presume that the timing generating and triggering mechanisms of the ICTM are only to be engaged by a very intense signal, as a means to transcend the 'normal' ups and downs in PF background activity and as to avoid being triggered by 'false positives' (CS lookalikes) .

Since probably any very strong signal can trigger the ICTM, the massive (unnatural) stimulation of PFs (as done by Johansson) did it too, and it will be argued that that is not the way in vivo, but in the meanwhile - as already said - it kept us on the wrong foot in understanding the CR by suggesting that the CS is coming in by the PFs .

I considered the excitatory NC (eNC) fibers sending a strongly LTP'd CS signal into the GrL, but it would 'disturb' way more PuCs than just those concerned in the involved nanoloops.

I also never encountered any mention of a 'direct eNC tract', i.e. one that is not formed by the collaterals of NI output neurons and hence the use of it would also send the amplified CS immediately to the reflex actuators, which would be counter the intention of having the reflex a bit delayed.

These collaterals better be used to feed output originating in the NI back into the GrL, since that information might be very useful for other purposes.

[13] Ankri et al. (2015)

“A less-known nucleo-cortical circuit is formed by the glutamatergic neurons of the CN which, in addition to projecting to various premotor and associative regions of the brain (Tsukahara and Bando, 1970; Asanuma et al., 1980; Angaut et al., 1985; Sultan et al., 2012; Ruigrok and Teune, 2014), send axonal collaterals to the cerebellar granule cell layer (GrCL; Houck and Person, 2015) .

These collateral fibers form MF-like terminals contacting granule cell (GrC) and Golgi cell dendrites (see also Tolbert et al., 1976, 1977, 1978; Ha'mori et al., 1980; Payne, 1983) .

The functional significance of this excitatory nucleo-cortical (eNC) pathway, loosely following the modular arrangement of the cerebellum (Dietrichs and Walberg, 1979; Gould, 1979; Haines and Pearson, 1979; Tolbert and Bantli, 1979; Buisseret-Delmas, 1988; Provini et al., 1998; Ruigrok, 2010 ; reviewed by Houck and Person, 2013), is likely related to efference copying of motor commands to the cerebellar cortex (Sommer and Wurtz, 2008; Houck and Person, 2015) .”

There is also the inhibitory NC (iNC) fiber tract to consider, which might - by inhibiting (a type of) GoCs which then disinhibit GrCs - create a strong signal by inundating the PuCs with the traffic 'from below' (if there is one), but this option is to be discarded since this tract is observed to be still more widely diverging.

[14] Giovannucci et al. (2017)

“Deep nuclear activity can lead to net excitation of GrCs by two routes: monosynaptic excitation, via collaterals of principal cells that terminate as mossy fibers, and disynaptic disinhibition, via inhibitory deep nuclear neuron projections onto Golgi cells, which in turn inhibit GrCs .”

[13] Ankri et al. (2015)

“Inhibitory GABA-glycinergic neurons of the cerebellar nuclei (CN) project profusely into the cerebellar cortex, where they make synaptic contacts on a GABAergic subpopulation of cerebellar Golgi cells. These spontaneously firing Golgi cells are inhibited by optogenetic activation of the inhibitory nucleo-cortical fibers both in vitro and in vivo. Our data suggest that the CN may contribute to the functional recruitment of the cerebellar cortex by decreasing Golgi cell inhibition onto granule cells.”

“A major feature of the iNC projection to the cortex is its divergence: upon relatively localized viral injection in the CN entire lobules may be innervated. Furthermore, single iNC axons traverse long distances along the medio-lateral plane, similarly to the PFs, making numerous contacts on individual Golgi cell dendrites.”

With the CSs being generated in the outside world, we tend to see MFs and PFs as the sole possible ways to bring this information to the PuCs, and yet we all know that the CFs are the main messengers to announce the presence of the US.

The drawbacks of a CS coming in via PFs or AFs (and hence GrL-MFs) were already discussed, and the CFs - at least by their layout in the cortical circuitry and their signalling characteristics - appeared to be better candidates (no 'parcellation' of PuCs, no power problem, strong outstanding signal), but it was left in the dark how CFs might become 'CS-carriers' to begin with.

An article by Ten Brinke et al. in which it is proposed that the amplified CS might be channeled to the IO by the nucleo-olivary route, where the strong and sudden inhibition provokes rebound firing in CFs (based on the observation of CS related complex spikes in the PuCs), gives a strong indication that the CFs also announce the presence of the CS to the PuCs, but Ten Brinke et al. do not conceive it as a possible ICTM trigger although being aware of Johansson's research.

[15] Bazzigaluppi et al. (2012)

“Our results show how IO neurons respond to CN stimulation sequentially with : i) a short depolarization (EPSP), ii) a hyperpolarization (IPSP) and iii) a rebound depolarization.”

[6] Ten Brinke et al. (2015)

“The presence of the CS-complex spike means the CS-encoding signal has acquired the means to reach the olivary nucleus. Insofar as the eyeblink paradigm used here contains an operant component in that the CR can reduce the aversive impact of the air puff US (Longley and Yeo, 2014), cerebral cortical involvement might possibly be involved. In any case, the strong Purkinje cell-wise link between the occurrence of CS-complex spikes and the magnitude of simple spike suppression suggests interdependent plasticity mechanisms underlying both phenomena. An interesting possibility is that loops within the olivocerebellar network could play a role. The origin of the CS-complex spike could lie in the mossy fiber collaterals to the cerebellar nuclei that are newly formed over the course of conditioning (Boele et al., 2013), which could establish a straightforward bridge to cross for CS-encoding signals to directly hook up to the nucleo-olivary pathway (De Zeeuw et al., 1988) .”

“The resulting CS-activated olivary inhibition could then bear rebound spikes (Bazzigaluppi et al., 2012; De Gruijl et al., 2012) that return to the cerebellum to affect cortical activity in a number of ways. It could influence simple spike suppression through the climbing fiber pause (De Zeeuw et al., 2011), through non-synaptic activation of MLIs (Jörntell and Ekerot, 2003; Szapiro and Barbour, 2007; Mathews et al., 2012), as well as through several climbing fiber-dependent forms of cerebellar cortical plasticity (Gao et al., 2012) .”

“In addition to Purkinje cells, parallel fiber activity encoding the CS reaches molecular layer interneurons (MLIs) through excitatory synapses, which can probably be strengthened through concomitant climbing fiber activity and, thereby, in principle, contribute to eyeblink conditioning (Gao et al., 2012) . However, having shown that conditioned Purkinje cell simple spike suppression seems to persist after blocking cerebellar cortical feedforward synaptic inhibition provided by MLIs, Hesslow and colleagues are now homing in on potential mechanisms intrinsic to Purkinje cells (Johansson et al., 2014) .”

Yet, the inherently very strong firing of the CFs, targeting directly the PuCs, bypassing the GrL, makes them the perfect messengers to 'tell' the PuCs that a CS is present.

And so the nucleo-olivary neurons (NONs) come into focus as the NuCs which associate MF and CF input, LTP their MF-NON synapses when the association is consistent and start to HP-R the ION downstream when a CS arrives through sufficiently LTP'd synapses, resulting in a CF activation that 'informs' the PuC of the beginning of a CS.

I believe it is only logical that the NONs have been included in the PPC formation (and hence in nanoloops), if not by 'simple apposition' to the major outputting NuCs, then also (and maybe better) by having been subjected to the same HP-R regime by PuCs in early life.

[12] Uusisaari et al. (2011)

“Such pauses, proposed to occur after complex spikes, could initiate rebound burst firing (note that the GABAergic CN neurons seem to exhibit a somewhat stronger bursting phenotype than the glutamatergic CN neurons; Uusisaari et al. 2007) .”

I comment on a number of articles that seem to undermine the above view in the discussion.

4) RECAPITULATION

Taking the stand that the PuCs have to recognize a CS over background by the intensity of the signal, the candidate routes by which the NI might provide such a signal to the PuCs are screened.

The eNC and iNC tracts lack in target specificity and carry signals of their own that better be left undisturbed.

The characteristics of the CF route (strong signal, targeting whole PuCs) make it much better suited to deliver a 'loud, clear and unequivocal' signal, and it is Ten Brinke et al. which infer from the observation of 'CS-related complex spikes' that the CS 'reaches the IO', and that the MF-CS signal is transferred to the CFs by this little detour.

Hence it is logically proposed that the NONs are the cells on which MF synapses are to be LTP'd, and it is assumed that these NONs only HP-R (the IONs of) the CFs belonging to their own nanoloops.

It is another example of PPC formation, now concerning the CS carrying MFs, enabling a specific CS to trigger a NON (group) to HP-R an ION (group).

5) COHABITATION

The emerging picture is that - when it comes to creating and executing CRs - the whole procedure can leave GrL activity in the microzone totally unperturbed, and free in doing whatever it was busy with.

The striking observation of Wada et al. can be explained by it : learning the CR does not need a GrC mediated CS, but its expression needs PuC activity.

[16] Wada et al. (2007)

“The results thus indicate that the failure of DOX-treated RNB mice to express CRs depends on the expression of tetanus toxin that results in blockade of granule cell transmission to Purkinje cells. Collectively, these results explicitly demonstrate that the memory of eyeblink CRs is acquired and saved despite the absence of the CS signals to Purkinje cells and also indicate that the normal granule cell transmission is necessary for expression of the stored memory of eyeblink conditioning.”

It pleads at least for the initiating process of the ICTM to be CF and not AF/PF dependent (the timer selecting process is in any case US-CF dependent) .

The lack of CR expression in the Wada experiment might be explained by the fact that HP'ing a PuC is of no consequence when the PuC is already silent, and hence it leaves us in the dark as to the question if the timer was activated (by CF input) or not (by lack of GrC mediated CS input), but I prefer the CF option for the reasons given earlier.

It is to be said that Wada et al. find it difficult to explain the utter PuC silence when spontaneous activity is expected, MLIs are not activated and the IO feedback loop does not react.

[16] Wada et al. (2007)

“The difference in the firing mechanism of Purkinje cells between this study and other studies remains elusive.”

“Previous electrophysiological recording in isolated/slice preparations or in anesthetized animals indicated that Purkinje cells fire spontaneously in the absence of synaptic input. In contrast to these findings, blockade of granule cell transmission abolished firing of simple spikes in the DOX-treated awake animals.”

“In the cerebellar cortical circuitry, basket, stellate, and Golgi interneurons receive granule cell transmission and could influence the responsiveness of Purkinje cells. However, these interneurons are all inhibitory and would facilitate firing of simple spikes by blockade of granule cell transmission. No such facilitation of simple spike firing was observed in the DOX-treated RNB mice.”

“The cerebellar nuclei also send inhibitory projections to the inferior olive. It is thus possible that blockade of granule cell transmission leads to a reduction in inhibition in the cerebellar nuclei, which could in turn result in inhibition in the inferior olive via the nuclear-olivary inhibitory pathway. However, we observed no change in either the pattern or the frequency of complex spikes elicited by the climbing fiber input.”

Anyway : it opens the possibility that these microzones and NI reflex regions are not 'just' implementing CRs, and that they might also serve a completely different purpose.

Or do we have to put it the other way round : producing CRs might be a 'side job' - done by means that can 'cohabitate' with the basic function.

6) TIMELINE

Let's now put the CR formation as proposed here in a timeline.

A) TRAINING PHASE :

When CS MF activity consistently precedes US CF induced HP-R in the NI (via the PuCs), the active MF-NuC synapses on ... GABA-ergic NONs are LTP'd, the inactive ones are LTD'd (a rule that has to be added), and the active MF terminals are induced to sprout.

[9] Nishiyama (2014)

“These results indicate that eyelid conditioning strengthens CS pathway to the nucleus by de novo formation of mossy fiber inputs carrying CS. Since the nucleus contains a mixture of excitatory and inhibitory neurons, future studies must address whether the postsynaptic targets of these learning-induced new mossy fiber inputs are excitatory or inhibitory.”

“It is highly likely that the reduction of perineuronal nets removes local inhibitory cues, which causes the growth of presynaptic inputs in the deep cerebellar nuclei.”

It requires the CS to be present at US time (not necessarily continuous from the start) .

With LTP developing in the NONs, the NONs start to 'grow' also a PPC with these specific CS-MFs (notwithstanding eventual MF map scrambling), meaning that ultimately they acquire the capacity to HP-R an ION all by themselves (while nonetheless keeping in touch with many other MFs, analogous to the connectivity with PuC axon terminals) .

When the PPC becomes 'mature', the ION is triggered into CS-related CF firing in these specific nanoloops already from the moment that the CS begins (but not necessarily extending it as the CS continues, since it is based on HP-R), but just this 'announcing' signal is enough to initiate the timer generating process of the ICTMs of the PuCs lying on these nanoloops.

A second CF burst (US triggered / maybe even more forceful / widely distributed to the whole involved reflex region) is needed to activate the timer selection process of the ICTMs (stabilizing timers tuned to a specific delay) .

This US CF burst might itself initiate ICTMs (e.g. in regions where the first CS related CF burst did not go), but with no second burst following, the ICTM process peters out without a timer selection phase.

Although the US CF signal is 'global' (meant to reach the whole microzone) while the CS CF signal is 'local' (only meant for the PuCs in nanoloops that have a PPC between the NON and the CS carrying MFs), it still would be handy if the individual PuC ICTMs could discriminate between the two signals as they are to trigger different ICTM processes : maybe the association with the concomitant arrival of the US signal by way of the MFs (and hence the AFs) can make the difference.

CS related CF bursts by the collaterals excite the NI output neurons of these nanoloops too, which might trigger early CRs if not inhibited to do so by the PuCs.

[17] Ohyama et al. (2001)

“The residual conditioned responses spared after cerebellar cortex removal, with their short and relatively fixed latencies to onset irrespective of the training interstimulus interval (ISI), are thought to reflect either plasticity in the AIN at the mossy fiber to nucleus cell synapse (Garcia and Mauk, 1998) or excitability changes in nucleus cells (Aizenman and Linden, 2000) .”

[18] Ten Brinke et al. (2017)

“Adaptive facilitatory responses are often preceded by acquired transient inhibition of IpN activity that, based on latency and effect, appear to be driven by complex spikes in cerebellar cortical Purkinje cells.”

[6] Ten Brinke et al. (2015)

“Recent findings showed conditioned simple spike suppression in the absence of MLI feedforward inhibition by GABAergic neurotransmission (Johansson et al., 2014) . Yet, the existence of conditioned CS-related complex spike responses reported here raises the possibility of conditioned CS-related MLI activation, either through glutamate spillover (Jörntell and Ekerot, 2003; Szapiro and Barbour, 2007) or ephaptic inhibition (Blot and Barbour, 2014) .”

HP-R in the IO also involves some delay, explaining that these effects - while 'early' - are not immediate.

[19] Rasmussen et al. (2013)

“An unusual but highly interesting feature of the nucleo-olivary pathway is the long delay between activation of the nucleo-olivary pathway and the inhibition of the inferior olive. If one stimulates the pathway directly using electrical stimulation, the main inhibition of the olive occurs with a 25–75 ms delay (Hesslow, 1986; Svensson et al., 2006).”

[20] Bengtson et al. (2006)

“The long latency of the inhibition elicited by direct stimulation of NO fibres is enigmatic.”
“The long latency of NO inhibition is caused by receptor properties.”

As long as the CR is too weak to tune down US provoked CF firing, the CS MFs sprout and engage more and more nanoloops to implement a stronger CR.

[21] De Zeeuw et al. (2015)

“Moreover, the mossy fiber collaterals on cerebellar nuclei neurons also show structural preterminal sprouting during conditioning, the amount of which correlates well with the amplitude of the conditioned responses (Boele et al. 2013).”

[19] Rasmussen et al. (2013)

“The Purkinje cell CR and the resulting inhibition of the inferior olive are an anticipation of the coming US signal. The suppression of the US signal, assuming it is delivered, will be proportional to the amount of learning that has taken place. We suggest that if the anticipated US intensity matches the actual US intensity, there will be no further plasticity in the cerebellar cortex, and in extension, there will be no further behavior modification. In other words, the cerebellar network will be at an equilibrium level where subsequent input, given that it does not deviate from prior input, will not induce further plasticity.”

B) TESTING PHASE :

When the timer units in the PuCs of the concerned nanoloops are formed, the start of the CS related CF burst triggers them into automatic action (the CS no more has to last as long as the ISI), HP'ing the PuCs after the calibrated delay, disinhibiting forcefully the partner output NuCs, provoking the overt CR .

[22] Jirenhed et al. (2011)

“It is worth noticing that the animals were trained with a delay paradigm in which the CS continues throughout the ISI. We are only claiming that a single pulse is all that is necessary to elicit a CR after it has already been learned. A sustained CS signal might still be necessary for learning.”

“We conclude that the time course of the Purkinje cell CR is determined by the initial part of the CS and is independent of the temporal pattern of parallel fiber activity during all but the very first few milliseconds (The ‘PF view’ ...). The results suggest that the initial part of the CS signal triggers a mechanism for reducing the Purkinje cell firing with a specific, but adjustable, delay and duration, and that once this mechanism is activated, it runs its course relatively independent of further input.”

The partner NONs are disinhibited too, and with the CR growing they tune down US related CF firing (the protective action of the CR also tunes the US itself down) , which in turn arrests further LTP and MF terminal sprouting.

C) EXTINCTION AND SAVINGS :

Extinction is due to the disappearance of timer action in the PuCs (active timers being removed until incapable of jointly evoking HP ?), but their remaining 'subclinical presence' might constitute an aspect of savings when their number increases again.

In the NI, LTP and MF sprouting might take much more time (if ever) to disappear, possibly explaining savings too.

[23] Kehoe et al. (2014)

“During changes in the cerebellar cortex during extinction, changes in synapses in the deep nuclei would remain largely intact (Perrett and Mauk 1995; Medina et al. 2002; Jirenhed et al. 2007; Kalmbach and Mauk 2012).”

7) THE SEGREGATION MECHANISM

[24] Kehoe et al. (2013) did research on conditioning with 'serial compound' CSs, in which he describes an unexplained phenomenon of 'displaced' CR timing due to the use of two different CSs following each other in time BEFORE the US is administered.

It is a case of CS interference with the restriction that the interference can only occur if the above training protocol is followed : it is not possible to create lasting interference just by training with a second CS 'outside' the CS-US ISI of the training with the first one, but in that case the 'double peaks' phenomenon can still transiently show in the beginning.

It suggested to me that there is a mechanism that prevents nanoloops to 'invest' in more than one CS : if training protocols place two CSs in competition (but on condition that the ISIs don't overlap), then a 'segregation' process will entail, forcing both CSs to 'bail out' of nanoloops used by the other one (and recruiting other 'free' nanoloops if need be) - a process of unstable equilibrium 'falling' one way or the other, favouring the 'most reinforced' CS .

In other words : when two different CSs are applied, the involved MF-NuC synapses are treated as 'being of one kind' if both CSs precede the US related HP-R - as they are being jointly LTP'd (the 'compound' situation of Kehoe - ISIs overlap) .

But if the ISIs do NOT overlap, CS1 synapses will be LTP'd while CS2 ones are LTD'd, and CS2 synapses will be LTP'd while CS1 ones are LTD'd, and the most frequently applied CS will win this game and subdue the other (in the nanoloops that have NuCs that connect to the two CS related MF modalities) .

If the SAME CS is used for training with two different ISIs however, then it is possible to get a form of CS interference with double-peaked CRs.

[17] Ohyama et al. (2001)

“Reversible disconnection of the cerebellar cortex shows that this learning occurs before detectable plasticity is established in the AIN. Subsequent conditioning with a shorter ISI in phase II induced plasticity in the AIN, as suggested by the presence of shortlatency responses. That this additional plasticity allows plasticity in the cerebellar cortex to be expressed as a double-peaked response on long CS trials is consistent with the view that the former plays a permissive role in conditioned response expression. That the timing of the second peak was appropriate for the long ISI is consistent with the hypothesis that plasticity in the cerebellar cortex is responsible for conditioned response timing.”

The local spatial distribution differences of the CS1 and CS2 MF-NuC synapses and the temporal component of the frequency of CS appliance together will determine how a 'mixed' CS12 region will segregate into CS1 and CS2 regions (containing different nanoloop sets) (it is probably wrong to say 'regions': the nanoloops may be spatially scattered).

Before segregation steps in, the overlap of the CS12 MF inputs may cause a 'learning to learn' effect (facilitating appearance of CRs to CS2, but it is to be explained by the availability of timers tuned to CS1 in the PuCs, and not by the existing LTP'd MF synapses for CS1 in the involved NuCs), and as long as the segregation is not completed, the interference should show by having CR2s timed to CS1.

[25] Kehoe (1995)

“After CRs were established to CSA, transfer training was begun: that is, CSA was dropped and a different signal CSB (e.g., light) was introduced. At the beginning of testing, CSB was presented four times by itself to determine whether there was any immediate transfer from CSA to CSB. In fact, immediate transfer was negligible. However, once CSB-US pairings were begun, learning to learn appeared: in other words, there was very rapid CR acquisition during CSB-US pairings as compared to the rate of CR acquisition in a set of control groups.”

“Learning to learn in classical conditioning of rabbits displays two key features that appear in other species and other tasks. First, the transfer occurs between signals of different sensory modalities and thus transcends the lack of physical similarity between the stimuli. Second, learning to learn does not depend on maintenance of the CR to CSA. Specifically, Kehoe, Morrow, and Holt (1984) deliberately extinguished the initial CR to CSA by repeatedly presenting CSA without the US. After the CR to CSA had been extinguished, CSB-US training was started. The CR acquisition to CSB was rapid, and equally as rapid as in a group that had been permitted to retain the original CR to CSA.”

If HP not followed by a US is the mechanism for extinction, then further decline of timers stops when their summed effort is no more able to provoke HP of the PuC : it means that a deliberate extinction procedure (as Kehoe et al. undertake here before starting training with the second CS) can abolish a CR but cannot really 'eradicate' the timers (they persist in 'subclinical' numbers – cfr the 'power' problem : not able to jointly cause HP any more), which might explain 'learning to learn' to persist even when the first CR is extinguished (in fact, Kehoe, long before the ICTM concept was formulated, in principle explains the same with his 'minimal network', see [25] Kehoe (1995) page 4).

Full-blown CS interference ('cross-modal transfer') however is observed in juvenile animals : the tentative explanation I offer for this is that PPC formation has not yet been completed, and with nanoloops not yet formed, the segregation of CSs gets very difficult.

[26] Brown et al. (2008)

“Evidence of cross-modal transfer of ISI-specific response features has been demonstrated in our laboratory using a version of the differential conditioning procedure employed in rabbit EBC (Green Steinmetz, 2005; Kehoe et al., 1989 - Experiment 3; Kehoe, Horne, Horne, 1993; Mauk Ruiz, 1992) that we have adapted for rats (Brown, Pagani, Stanton, 2006) .

In this “ISI discrimination” task, subjects are trained in a delay EBC procedure using within-sessions presentations of two distinct CSs – one CS (e.g., tone) is conditioned at a short ISI (280 ms) and the other CS (e.g., light) is conditioned at a long ISI (880 ms) .

When training commences at PD23 or 30, conditioning to the long CS is strongly influenced by the short CS-US pairing, as evidenced by earlier peak latencies, enhanced CR amplitudes, and increased frequency of double-peaked CRs to the long CS relative to controls that do not receive paired short CS-US presentations.

However, ISI discrimination performance in adults (PD80+ at the start of training; Brown et al. – Experiment 3) does not demonstrate the magnitude of influence of short ISI conditioning upon performance to the long CS observed in younger subjects.

Enhanced cross-modal transfer from the short to long CS in ISI discrimination diminishes – and temporal precision of CRs to the long CS improves between (approximately) PD30-80."

"While crossmodal transfer has been documented across multiple species, age ranges, and conditioning procedures (Campolattaro Freeman, 2006; Duong, Brown, Stanton, 2007; Frieman Goyette, 1973; Kehoe Holt; Molina et al.; Spear and Molina; Thomas, Miller, & Svinicki, 1971), the neurobiological mechanisms underlying ontogenetic changes in this phenomenon are currently unknown."

"The enhanced cross-modal transfer of EBC observed in PD23 and 30 rats trained in ISI discrimination may therefore reflect some functional immaturity of neural systems that increases the likelihood of generalization across distinct CSs due to a combination of (1) enhanced amodal processing and (2) a reliance on using common outcomes as a basis for unity."

A demo program was written to 'visualize' the segregation process, and to get more insight into the requirements to achieve it.

8) THE SEGREGATION DEMO

A) SETTING THE STAGE

Fig 1 : start of the demo run (200 steps)

Identify on the left the upper red line representing an MF carrying CS1 (say a 'tone' CS), and the lowest blue line representing an MF carrying CS2 (say a 'light' CS) : both MFs have terminals that fan out to a column of 20 cyan-coloured NONs and the lines being 'dashed' means that the connections are still very weak or virtually nonexistent.

The small figures to the right of each NON indicate the 'absolute' SSs of the red and blue inputs at each NON (with decimals), the integers reflect their relative proportion (a %).

The sum of these red resp. blue input SSs appears at the MF origin, along with the number of terminals that connect to the NONs.

The NONs at their turn 'connect' to a column of PuCs with horizontal lines, but in fact it is meant to express that CFs inform the 'partner' PuCs of CS presence when MF-NON synapses are LTP'd enough to allow NONs to HP-R IONs, activating the 'CF-line'.

A thin CF-line means that the amount of LTP on the MF-NON synapses is still unable to 'activate' this line. The colour of this line (and of the PuC it connects to) represents the proportional mixture of the red and blue components of the CSs that impinge onto each NON, hence it is purple in the beginning, but with segregation proceeding it will turn red or blue.

The trials in the demo will be 'intermixed' i.e. at each loop a random factor gives a 50-50 chance to activate CS1 or CS2.

CS1 is supposed to be followed by the US after an ISI of 800 ms, while for CS2 the ISI=400 ms.

Also on the left but in the space between the outer lines, you see two 'flat curves' : they are 'waiting' for a CR to emerge in the form of a 'Gaussian', the CR for CS2 will appear in the blue section (the first 400 ms), the CR for CS1 in the red section (from 400 to 800 ms).

The upper 'Gaussians' will reflect the CR strengths when testing with CS1 after x 'steps' or (intermixed) training trials, the lower ones do the same for testing with CS2 .

They will show very clearly what is called 'the double peak phenomenon'.

The demo, of course, is a 'schematic display' but it suffices to demonstrate the principle of the segregation process.

B) THE MF-NON PPC FORMATION PHASE

Let's run the demo a little while longer :

Fig. 2 (330 – 340 – 350 steps)

MF-terminal lines start thickening to render increasing LTP of the MF-NON synapses - perforce in discrete steps from one to 10 (10 being regarded as the saturation level) while LTP actually is gradual.

Thickening of the CF-line (in one step) renders the crossing of a threshold when CFs start to fire - and watch the numbers indicating increasing Ss (and sums) .

CR Gaussians (just a way to represent emergent CRs) appear when the joined effort of PuCs start to evoke an overt CR.

From each PuC and progressing to the right a 'beam' will appear : it is an evocation of the relative strengths of 'red' and 'blue' input respectively, by a rendering of the mixed background colour : it will start with 'purple' (being the mixture of 50-50 red and blue), but will 'segregate' later into red or blue. CF-lines and PuCs change colours accordingly.

Let's run the demo still further :

Fig. 3 (360 – 420 – 470 steps)

CRs develop and we arrive in the stage of the 'double peaks' phenomenon, meaning that both CSs can trigger each other CRs (cross-modal transfer).

C) THE SEGREGATION PHASE

All this went fairly quickly, but now a slow segregating process is starting up :

Fig. 4 (860 – 1380 – 2190 steps)

Double peaks start to dwindle, PuCs (nanoloops in fact) are ‘forced’ to choose between red or blue.

The end result is a complete segregation of CS1 and CS2 inputs onto different 'nanoloop' sets : no purple any more but just 'red and blue'. Observe that MF terminals were more or less halved in number (each NON now just receives one MF-terminal : MF-NON connections LTP'd to saturation – a PPC – or LTD'd into insignificance or plain disconnection). Double-peaked CRs gave way to the expected single-peaked CR : cross-modal transfer is no more. The ‘beam’ evokes the segregation history.

Fig. 5

See a complete demo run with :

<https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fi/abbzv0is3venjueum5dup/demo-3-4.mp4?rlkey=q4pbnxzhlt9agmh75x8xbrfl&dl=0>

To obtain this result several parameters came into play :

LTP (SS increase) affects MF-NON synapses when they are ACTIVE (implied : during US CF firing) and is set to be :

- proportional to the actual SS of this synapse
- proportional to an LTP gain factor
- inversely proportional to the distance to saturation (10-SS) upwards from a given threshold
- inversely proportional to the summed strength of all active CS (tone or light) SSs, also upwards from a given threshold, i.e. the threshold above which CF firing starts, reasoning that the ensuing CR strength increases in parallel with the summed SS and that this CR gradually subdues the US and hence further timer production in the PuCs : we can interpret it to say that LTP increase is also a function of US strength.

Finally the resulting increase is multiplied with a % of a pure random factor (from 0 to 1).

LTD (SS decrease) affects the MF-NON synapses which are INACTIVE (whilst the others are active) and it is set to be :

- proportional to the actual SS of this synapse
- proportional to an LTD gain factor
- and also proportional to the actual SS of the ACTIVE MF-NON synapse, and hence all factors determining LTP on the active synapse indirectly also determine LTD at the inactive one.

(Always remember that in this 'schematic' demo ONE synapse is to represent a set of synapses onto ONE NON).

When SS almost reaches zero (0.1) the concerned MF-NON terminal is 'cut' and disappears.

An MF line 'gets a chance to (re)connect' (using a random factor again), but this chance is also proportional to US strength (which declines once a CR starts to develop), in other words : the stronger the US the more incentive for MF terminal spread and new synapse formation (it might be analogous to the influence of US strength upon LTP) .

The interplay between LTP and 'connection speed' proved very important since LTP and LTD create a competition between CS1 and CS2 synapses in a NON, with growing LTP on active ones increasing LTD on inactive ones.

To allow for a situation in which initial double peaks can appear, both CSs must have the occasion to 'connect' quickly (or to have already connections from the start), so as to get some strength before any difference in SSs (together with a declining US) starts to disrupt the balance, forcing NONs which had connections with MFs from CS1 as well as CS2 'to choose sides'.

The rule of proportionality with US strength allows for an initial phase in which such 'double connections' can be made.

Strikingly, the random factor for LTP is a necessity to push the 'unstable equilibrium' out of balance as to initiate the segregation (yet, on occasions a switch can be observed !).

In the following demo stills, the 'beam' is replaced by a 'trace' (progressing from the PuCs to the right) : it is a red and a blue line representing the strength of 'red' and 'blue' input respectively, and when CFs start to fire the lines will start to diverge, one going up (strengthening) until saturation, one going down (weakening) until 'zero'.

Using 10 NONs, see the traces diverging when the random factor is non-zero, and see the rigid stability when it is disabled (in the last demo still), segregation unable to initiate, and double peaks persisting (fig. 6).

Fig. 6

See complete demo runs with random factor > 0 and = 0 :

<https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fi/772dk3jwx94ripy770356/demo-3-5.mp4?rlkey=aojvdde5cwoikhxzhv3zpaqs&dl=0>
<https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fi/8uig6pwq4gh9ddpdt1jwl/demo-3-6.mp4?rlkey=hitp8izzdkut8r2hjvumk08eb&dl=0>

D) THE TRANSFER TRAINING PROBLEM

When 'testing' the demo in a situation where CS1 is already established before training with CS2 begins ('transfer training'), a problem arises.

See fig. 7 : CS1 is established, but then CS2 is activated, and finally the demo switches to CS1 again : each time we see a complete 'takeover' by the next CS of the 'territory' occupied by the former one ('trace' and 'beam' are both 'on' in all the following demos).

Fig. 7 <https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fi/47j5x1kaxwsd5cstli1x9/demo-3-7.mp4?rlkey=mevbb6h8py1g21jynhugv1cmh&dl=0>

In vivo, when CS1 is established, training with CS2 will not extinguish CS1

The problem can be solved to great extent by making terminal spread (the chance to connect) inversely proportional to the amount of LTP in the NON (and hence can be different for each NON).

Having a 'ceiling' (saturation point) for LTP is a necessity in neurons like NONs in which a competition between MF synapses is to fall one way or the other (as conceived here), but this 'ceiling' should not be rendered meaningless by unbridled formation of new synapses which also start to undergo LTP.

If a 'total amount of LTP' is to be kept under control, 'saturation' should not be viewed as a process local to the synapse, but as a whole cell phenomenon.

A limit might be imposed on LTP by the dynamic equilibrium of receptor turnover, i.e. the cell - metabolically - might be programmed to provide resources that can only sustain a limited total level of LTP... .

I call it 'the metabolic brake'. In fact, I already used 'inverse proportionality with distance to saturation' in the formula to calculate LTP increase, and it looks just reasonable to introduce this factor as well in the formula that calculates terminal connection speed : after all, there is not much functional difference between LTP'ing a synapse and forming an extra one (I regard the US still as necessary to incite MF terminal sprouting but for 'braking reasons' the 'metabolic brake' can replace it here).

With the 'metabolic brake' incorporated we get fig. 8a : CS2 'takes over' but instead of 'killing' CS1 altogether it only about halves its CR power. When CS1 and CS2 are delivered intermixedly the metabolic brake does not undo (i.e. it preserves) the transient phase of the 'double peak' phenomenon (figs 8b and c).

Figs 8a

8b

8c

<https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fi/2jfvaawt17jfyv7jw3m83/demo-3-8.mp4?rlkey=kd42i7kjinwit54d6gsje2m15n&dl=0> 8a
<https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fi/9z7m66bp83gb3duzartdr/demo-3-9.mp4?rlkey=dn0viubdgar0r3roz0ljq9jb&dl=0> 8bc

The 'metabolic brake' (as implemented in the demo), however, proved to be insufficient to prevent complete takeover in the long run : if the demo is kept running longer than necessary (continuing CS2 training while its CR power is already sufficient), it appears that CS1 CR power is still eroding away very slowly.

I interpreted it as a remnant US effect, since a negative feedback on it can never silence it for 100 % (maybe we better look at a 'remnant US' as a US that occurs now and then, and not as a 'weak' US, since the underlying mechanism to provoke LTP is HP-R, which I regard to be an all-or-none phenomenon) .

However, when CS1 jumps in again, its CR power is almost immediately restored while now (the already stronger) CS2 CR power starts eroding.

It suggests the finishing touch : the trick to safeguard against mutual CR power erosion while preserving the 'double peak' phenomenon, is to allow for a very occasional activation of CS1 while CS2 is active (and vice versa) .

In vivo this might be implemented by a very low level of 'background noise', activating synapses at random even when the related CS is not present (during the US applied to train for the other one).

In the demo it solves the erosion problem completely.

E) RECAPITULATION

The demo shows that a nanoloop population receiving double intermixed CS input can segregate itself into two populations each receiving one CS input, and I searched for 'governing rules' that would respect some key CS observations. If these same rules are followed in vivo remains to be seen, of course.

The evolving balance between the formation of MF-NON synapses and the subsequent LTP/LTD competition proved important : the 'double peak' phenomenon requires that - initially - double connections (from both CSs) can form easily, but quickly the interplay between LTP and LTD starts to prune one or the other.

A random factor, natural in vivo, but not in silico, must be added, for without it, the 'symmetry' of the balance cannot be broken.

In the NON the US is needed to generate LTP, and US decline with a growing CR will bring LTP to a halt, but this 'US based brake' only affects the active synapses, and hence - when 'transfer training' with another CS is started - the newly activated synapses can merrily start growing LTP until they overpower the others, since the now inactive synapses of the former CS (and hence its CR) are being extinguished.

To avoid this unwanted phenomenon, another 'brake', based on the 'total NON LTP' should be introduced, such as to obstruct 'upcoming synapses' to be LTP'd when others (even when inactive) have already 'colonized' the NON, suggesting that a NON metabolically limits its resources to sustain LTP (or has another feedback system to obtain the same result) .

The same rules which govern LTP should govern the formation of new synapses : US strength inciting it, but the metabolic brake bringing it to a halt, and it is the individual NON which ultimately regulates the ease by which it can be synapsed upon.

Since a negative feedback can never completely eliminate an error, a remnant US will still allow active new synapses to grow LTP, and since these very slowly erode the LTP of the inactive ones, even a 'metabolic brake' guarding the total sum of LTP cannot avoid a 'takeover' in the long run. Allowing a very small amount of 'background noise' randomly activating synapses without the presence of the related CS is a very effective antidote against this erosion.

DISCUSSION

Several experiments seem to undermine the proposed view by implicitly suggesting that the CS must be channeled to the PuCs by other (MF) ways.

Kalmbach assumes that blocking the NO route by muscimol prevents extinction (in delay conditioning).

[27] Kalmbach et al. (2012)

“Preventing cerebellum-mediated extinction by silencing neurons in DCN. Silencing DCN neurons with infusions of the GABAA receptor agonist muscimol not only prevents DCN-mediated inhibition of the climbing fibers during the CS but also prevents the expression of conditioned responses (Chapman et al. 1990; Garcia and Mauk 1998; Hardiman et al. 1996; Kalmbach et al. 2009; Ramnani and Yeo 1996). Because of this, the ability of a muscimol infusion to block extinction must be inferred from levels of responding during the postmuscimol extinction session the next day (Ramnani and Yeo 1996).”

There is no expression of the CR during muscimol blocking and the persistence of the CR is inferred from testing after the washout. However, it can be interpreted that the PuCs simply did not receive the CF mediated CS signal (since the NONs were silenced), which by itself prevents extinction (extinction of PuC timers is supposed to occur when an actual CS signal is not followed by the US), and these experiments tried to reveal the 'prevention' of a process that simply could not have taken place : it was assumed that a timer triggering CS signal reached the PuCs via the MFs, quod non.

The experiment of Medina with picrotoxin (blocking the output of NONs instead of inhibiting them by muscimol), logically then, 'prevents' extinction in the same way and is to be re-explained in the same way.

[28] Medina et al. (2002)

“During intra-olivary infusion of picrotoxin, the same four rabbits maintained robust response levels throughout the entire extinction session.”

His converse experiment - blocking stimulation of the IO by NBQX - cuts the power of the US to fire CFs, but does not necessarily prevent CFs to be fired by HP-R in the IO by the NONs, and that explains extinction of a CR even with an everpresent US (PuCs receive the CS signal but the US signal cannot reach them).

[28] Medina et al. (2002)

“Continuous infusion of NBQX (150mM, 0.1 ml min⁻¹) during a subsequent tone plus unconditioned stimulus session resulted in the gradual disappearance of conditioned eyelid responses, until only the reflex response to the reinforcing unconditioned stimulus remained. The decline in conditioned response during infusion of NBQX was statistically indistinguishable from that observed during normal tone-alone extinction training in the same four animals.”

Hence, the interpretation above can replace Medina's interpretation that CF firing frequency determines learning (when increased) and extinction (when decreased below equilibrium level) and decouples it from his supposition that LTD/LTP at the PF-PuC synapse is to sculpt a CR.

[28] Medina et al. (2002)

“As recording data have shown that the ability of the unconditioned stimulus to activate climbing fibres is inhibited during a conditioned response, the simulations suggest that a simple extension of this hypothesis may explain the present infusion results : that is, strong inhibition during a conditioned response at a time when the unconditioned stimulus is omitted (as with extinction training) drives climbing fibre activity below its equilibrium level, thereby signalling the induction of plasticity responsible for extinction.”

“Omitting the unconditioned stimulus after acquisition, or blocking the excitatory input to the climbing fibre as with NBQX infusion, tipped the balance in favour of inhibition, and thus promoted extinction by causing climbing fibre activity during the trial to fall well below equilibrium.”

“Conversely, although omitting the unconditioned stimulus during extinction training removed the strong excitatory input from the unconditioned stimulus, simulated infusion of picrotoxin also blocked the strong inhibitory input associated with making a conditioned response. Thus, climbing fibre activity did not decrease below the spontaneous level during the trial and extinction was prevented.”

“Our infusion data support the hypothesis that the induction of extinction is signalled by a decrease in climbing fibre activity during the tone, and that this decrease is produced by strong response-associated inhibition occurring in the absence of the excitatory drive from the omitted unconditioned stimulus.”

“The simulation incorporated a site of plasticity in the cerebellar cortex on the basis of observations that co-activation of granule cells and climbing fibres induces long-term depression (LTD) of granule to Purkinje synapses, whereas granule activity alone induces long-term potentiation (LTP) . Thus, the bi-directional modulation of climbing fibre activity was responsible for acquisition and extinction of eyelid responses through the induction of LTD and LTP, respectively.”

The experiments of Carrel et al. are conflicting with those of Medina : they also block US input into the IO (by local injection of a glutamate antagonist) but demonstrate that a CR can still be acquired, and that casts serious doubts upon the role of the US and the CFs themselves.

[29] Carrel et al. (2013)

“The ability to acquire CRs with IO unconditioned stimulus signals that were blocked or severely suppressed suggests that mechanisms responsible for CR acquisition are extremely resilient and probably less dependent on IO-task-related signals than previously thought.”

“The simplest explanation for this observation is that glutamate-mediated IO US signals perhaps contribute to, but are not required for, CR acquisition. This contradicts a major tenet of the cerebellar learning hypothesis, which states that IO US signals are pivotal for learning.”

“If this is the case, then the underlying mechanism would have to be remarkably resilient to withstand IO DGG-induced shifts in the spontaneous activity of the cerebellar cortex and nuclei and would have to rely on mossy fibers for both CS and US information.”

The authors suggest that it should be investigated if complex spikes still occur, to be sure that CF firing really was totally blocked, but apparently (and somewhat astonishingly) they leave it at that and I found no other research (combining IO glutamate blocking and complex spike monitoring) trying to prove the derived conclusions to be false (and if not false, why then is the US being sent to the IO ?) .

[29] Carrel et al. (2013)

“The most parsimonious interpretation of our data is that glutamate-mediated IO signals are not needed for acquisition. Testing this proposition will require careful electrophysiological studies, such as recording US-evoked Purkinje cell complex spike activity in eyeblink microzones, to determine whether the DGG doses reported here are indeed capable of completely blocking all IO US signals.”

However : the above experiment can be explained by assuming that the blocking injection is restricted to the IONs which are involved with a particular EBR-causing CS .

[29] Carrel et al. (2013)

“After tone training, DGG was administered to the contralateral dorsal accessory olive to determine the optimal location and dose needed for blocking glutamate neurotransmission in the eyeblink representation area (Weiss et al., 1993), as indexed by complete CR abolition (Zbarska et al., 2007) .”

“Determining IO injection sites : In the first part of the study, rabbits were subjected to functional mapping sessions in which they were injected with DGG (100 nmol/μl) to determine the optimal location and amount of DGG required to quickly abolish previously learned tone-evoked CRs.”

“If injections did not eliminate all IO US signals, then the residual US-evoked IO activity may have sufficed to support acquisition. However, this scenario seems unlikely. We incorporated multiple functional tests of injection effectiveness to reduce the likelihood of an incomplete block of US signals. Specifically, to ensure drug infusion into locations relevant to the eyeblink, *we selected only sites where small DGG injections abolished previously learned, tone CS-evoked CRs* (my italics) (Zbarska et al., 2007) .”

Indeed, with OCNO-philosophy maintained at the nanoloop level, the CF mediated CS signal only targets the IONs engaged in the nanoloops dedicated to this particular (tone) CS (and that would be ‘the optimal location’ in the IO for Carrel to inject his glutamate antagonist), while the set of EBR related IONs is much larger, and the set of IONs engaged for a CS consisting of a vibrissal airpuff – being segregated – is a different one). Hence, the ‘focused’ abolition of a tone induced CR does not necessarily prevent the acquisition of a vibrissal airpuff induced CR (by which Carrel is testing his hypothesis).

In the ‘segregated scenarios’ I always presume that the foregoing HP isolates the ION and keeps the activation focused by blocking the gap junctions, hence I assume the rebound to be as local as the HP.

[15] Bazzigaluppi et al. (2012)

“The GABAergic feedback input from the CN does not only temporarily block the transmission of signals through the IO, it also isolates neurons from the network by shunting the junction current and re-initiates the temporal pattern after a fixed time point”.

If the CS triggers CF firing by a rebound phenomenon induced by an inhibitory NON, it will not be blocked by a glutamate antagonist.

On the other hand the US impacts on the whole EBR region in the IO, and with gap junctions not blocked by GABA it will cause CFs to fire even if - locally - part of the US glutamate inputs are silenced.

If the 'local' CS triggered complex spikes and the 'global' US triggered complex spikes are evoked, then the ICTM will set up a timing for the CR even if the CR itself cannot be executed.

[29] Carrel et al. (2013)

“A potentially more selective method for blocking IO task-related signals is suppressing their US inputs by glutamate antagonists, which have been shown to block responses to trigeminal stimulation (Lang, 2001) and to reduce, but not abolish, the IO’s spontaneous firing rate (Lang, 2001). Even this relatively modest reduction of IO spontaneous firing has a major nonspecific effect on cerebellar output neurons—it silences them (Zbarska et al., 2007, 2008).”

An article by Aksenov et al. seems to plead against a role for MFs in the NI to produce CRs.

[30] Aksenov et al. (2005)

“Even though fast glutamate receptor-mediated neurotransmission seems to have an accessory role in the expression of previously learned eyeblink CRs, it is not essential because rabbits are able to produce CRs even when both AMPA/kainate and NMDA receptors are blocked. This finding fails to support the concepts postulating the critical role of glutamatergic inputs from collaterals of mossy and climbing fibers during the execution of conditioned eyeblinks.”

“As evidenced by the presence of CRs in animals injected with DGG, direct input from mossy fiber collaterals into the IN (which receives unobstructed information from the cerebellar cortex) is not required for, and therefore does not primarily drive, behavioral CRs.”

If true it would question the NI to be the site of association between the CS and the US, compelling to look again at the cerebellar cortex as the site where it is implemented. But what then is the purpose of specific CS terminal MF-sprouting which only occurs when a CR is to develop ?

Aksenov et al. seem convinced that the glutamate blocker completely abolishes MF influence (based on same dose effects in other areas), but nonetheless mention that there are dose related effects.

[30] Aksenov et al. (2005)

“The 1st DGG microinjection (49 μ mol) increased CR latency, had the tendency to decrease the amplitude of CRs, and slightly decreased CR incidence. The same effect was slightly more pronounced after the 2nd injection of DGG (an additional 49 μ mol).”

“After the 1st injection, CR latency significantly increased to 249.9 \pm 5.1 ms. After the 2nd injection of DGG, CR latency further increased to 253.5 \pm 5.5 ms. This increase, however, was not significant when compared with the 1st injection.”

“Injections of DGG decreased CR incidence in a dose dependent manner (Fig. 3). At the group level, CR incidence significantly decreased from the preinjection level of 90.2 \pm 0.65% to 73.2 \pm 1.9% after the 1st injection (trials 41–80) and to 63.2 \pm 3.6% after the 2nd injection (trials 81–200).”

It might be that the PPC is such an LTP saturated connection that it will be very difficult to silence it, in comparison with 'the usual' synapses, and hence a weakening but not a 100 % block is observed.

[30] Aksenov et al. (2005)

Even the highest concentration of DGG failed to abolish CRs.

The authors themselves are so baffled by the logical consequences of their observation (and interpretation of it) that they suggest that another - yet unknown - excitatory transmitter might be in play, not impossible of course.

[30] Aksenov et al. (2005)

Is it possible that mossy and climbing fibers use some other excitatory neurotransmitter in addition to glutamate ?

A weird result often indicates that something was wrong with the experimental paradigm, but sometimes it can indeed be the eye-opener that leads to unexpected insight

CONCLUSION

Demonstrating the feasibility of CS segregation in silico (with a demo that cannot be but a simplification) is no proof that it occurs in cerebello, but it provides a strong argument for it. Of course, actual research is to corroborate or to falsify this hypothesis.

The early but transient double peaks phenomenon (a short phase in which cross-modal transfer occurs when training for two different CSs with different ISIs) is quite an indication that a segregation mechanism must be at work and a host of observations point to the NI (the CN) and not to the cortex cerebelli as the site where it occurs. Same for the CS identification process since it involves the same synapses.

The NONs are the targets of preference and not the other outputting NuCs : while they probably all get converging MF and CF input – necessary to detect a recurrent association between CS and US – only NONs can reach the PuCs directly, by using the ‘nucleo-olivary bridge’ to the CFs, as demonstrated by [6] Ten Brinke et al. (2015) .

HP-R is involved twice : in the NON to induce LTP at the MF synapses, in the ION to fire the CF. (each time it is also a means to cause a depolarization although the impulse is given by an inhibiting neuron, and in the case of the ION it explains why – after due training – only the start of the CS matters, the rest of it being irrelevant).

HP-R in the NON also maintains LTP at specific PuC-NuC synapses after it was maximized in early life during the juvenile multi-innervation phase of CFs onto PuCs to implement the formation of PPCs and hence of nanoloops, which in turn allow for the existence of a segregation mechanism, as argued in [11] Beunis (2021a).

Analysis of the demo segregation algorithm in silico suggested that LTP and ‘budding’ (new synapse formation) are jointly actuated by CF firing (the US) and kept in bounds by a ‘whole cell metabolic brake’ on the cellular level (a parameter that had to be introduced to prevent ‘takeover’ in transfer training) and by declining US (by growing CR) at the population level.

Hence CS-MFs can recruit the nanoloop population that is necessary to evoke a CR by joint forces, but when a second CS is introduced it is forced to recruit another nanoloop set, and when they are introduced ‘intermixedly’ an LTP/LTD competition ensues that ends in a segregation, with equilibria toppling at the slightest random disturbance.

In the microzone only PuCs belonging to the CS recruited nanoloops get the announcement of the CS by way of the CFs, implying that the microzone also processes CSs in a segregated way (although the involved PuCs are anatomically scattered (*) due to the dispersion of the CF collaterals in the cortex).

(*) If ICTMs from scattered PuCs (in different folia !) are to act synchronously, then CF collaterals should calibrate their conduction speed in accordance with their lengths, and that is apparently the case. If the same can be said for the PF axons returning to the CN is an open question.

The nature of the CF signal is ideal for an ICTM that ultimately has to HP a whole PuC (as hypothesized by Johansson), a situation that by itself already requires a segregated approach. CSs conveyed by PFs or AFs would pose power and identification issues. US carrying AFs however might play a role for the ICTM to discriminate between a CS-CF signal and a US-CF one.

A hypothesis that includes many assumptions generally has but a low chance to be in line with the real state of affairs, but the interrelationships of these assumptions, providing a ‘coherence’ to the hypothesis improve these chances.

The ‘nucleo-olivary’ bridge [6] Ten Brinke et al. (2015) ‘solves’ a lot of contradicting evidence in several experimental setups. On the other hand, the joint use of CFs for both CS and US is like asking for problems : CS and US have to trigger different actions and hence interferences might occur, unless additional conditions (e.g. the US also being conveyed to the PuCs by MFs) allow to disentangle the conflicts.

I do not expect all the detailed assumptions ‘to stand’, what really matters is if the overall hypothesis resists falsifying.

Quite some aspects of it go against ‘beliefs in the field’ and as such it should provoke a lot of brainstorming, and eventually also invite to targeted new research.

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